

Dielectric Study of Solvent Effect in Carboxylic Acids

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Manuscript received 27 November 1978, accepted 8 May 1986

The dielectric constant variation method has been used to evaluate the dipole moment (μ), the Kirkwood correlation factor (g) and the association constant (K) of carboxylic acids in various solvents. From that, the effect of solvents on solute molecules are discussed.

In order to study the interaction of the neighbouring dipole, Kirkwood in collaboration with Frohlich¹ introduced a rigorous statistical mechanical model which gives the relation for the dielectric constant of a polar liquid as

$$g\mu^2 = \frac{9KT}{4\pi N} \frac{(\epsilon - \epsilon_\infty)(2\epsilon + \epsilon_\infty)}{(\epsilon_\infty + 2)^3}$$

where, ϵ is the dielectric constant of the solute, ϵ_∞ the dielectric constant of the induced polarisation, T the absolute temperature, K the Boltzmann's constant, N the Avogadro's number, μ the dipole moment of the solute and g the Kirkwood correlation factor. The physical meaning of g is the measure of the local ordering, that is the measure of the short-range inter-molecular forces, which leads to dipole-dipole interaction. If there is no specific interactions one has $g=1$, and the above equation reduces to the Onsager equation² of dielectrics. For associating compounds where the occurrence of hydrogen bonding makes the relevant assumption that only certain specific angle between the dipole of the neighbouring molecule are possible, the inter-molecular interaction may be represented by means of a simplified models. For polymers, the same model can be used if each segment is used as a separate entity of which the orientation of the dipole moment is correlated with the dipole moment of the other segments. In many cases, these models contain undetermined parameters so that the value of g is often calculated as an empirical quantity by the above equation and the dipole moment μ by the method Few and Symth³. The unknown parameters can be found from the experimental values of g . However, an experimental determination of g with concentration will give the quantitative information regarding the undetermined parameters and hence, the nature of the inter-molecular interaction in polar liquids.

Malecki⁴ studied the correlation factor g and the non-linear correlation factor due to the saturation effects in liquid complexes and from that he was able to decide whether the complex is of charge-transfer type or proton-transfer type etc. The static dielectric constant behaviour of mono-alcohols and their solutions in non-polar solvent⁵⁻⁸

was studied with special reference to the variation of g with concentration. And the variation of g of the acetic acid was discussed in the higher concentration by Sabesan and Varadarajan⁹.

Experimental

A WTW 01 dipolmeter at a frequency of 2 MHz was used to measure the dielectric constants keeping the cell temperature at 30°. The refractive indices were determined at 30° by Abbe's refractometer. Pure grade (E. Merck) solvents and solutes were purified by standard methods.

The evaluation of molar polarisation includes the measurement of dielectric constant (ϵ), refractive index (n) and density (d) of the mixtures at the different concentrations in the solvents.

Method of calculation: Considering each kind of polymer as a separate compound neglecting any specific correlation between the total dipole moment of the polymer, the dielectric equation can be written as

$$\frac{(\epsilon - 1)(2\epsilon + 1)}{12\pi\epsilon} = \frac{N\alpha_0}{1 - f_0\alpha_0} + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{N_n}{1 - f_n\alpha_n} \left(\alpha_n + \frac{\mu_n^2}{3KT} \frac{1}{1 - f_n\alpha_n} \right) \quad (2)$$

where, the suffix zero refers to the non-polar solvents and n refers to the polymer containing n -polar units. The average value of μ_n^2 is taken over all configurations of the multimeter. By substituting the appropriate values of $\alpha_0, \alpha_n, \frac{1}{1 - f_0\alpha_0}$ and $\frac{1}{1 - f_n\alpha_n}$ in equation (2),

$$\frac{\epsilon - 1}{12\pi\epsilon} = \frac{N_0(\epsilon_0 - 1)M_0}{4\pi(2\epsilon + \epsilon_0)d_0N_A} + \frac{(\epsilon_\infty - 1)M_1}{4\pi(2\epsilon + \epsilon_\infty)d_1N_A} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} N_n + \frac{(2\epsilon + 1)(\epsilon_\infty + 2)^3}{27KT(2\epsilon + \epsilon_\infty)^3} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} N_n \mu_n^2 \quad (3)$$

Since there is no correlation between the different chain, g_n represents the total correlation between permanent moment of the segment in the n -mer and its surroundings.

The Kirkwood correlation factor, g , can be written as

$$g = \frac{\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} n N_n g_n}{\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} n N_n} = \frac{\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} N_n \bar{\mu}_n^2}{\mu^2 \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} n N_n} \quad (4)$$

By using the mole fraction of the solvent X_1 and that of the solute X_2 , the equation for the Kirkwood correlation factor, g , is given by

$$g = \left[\frac{9KT}{4\pi N} \frac{(2\epsilon + \epsilon_\alpha)^2}{2X_2(\epsilon_\alpha + 2)^2(2\epsilon + 1)} \right] \left[\phi \frac{\epsilon - 1}{\epsilon} - \frac{3X_1\phi_1(\epsilon_1 - 1)}{2\epsilon + \epsilon_1} - \frac{3X_2\phi_2(\epsilon_\alpha - 1)}{(2\epsilon + \epsilon_\alpha)} \right] \quad (5)$$

where, ϵ_1 and ϕ_1 , and ϵ and ϕ are the dielectric constant and molar volume of the solvent and the solution, respectively.

Results and Discussion

The calculated values of dipole moment μ , Kirkwood correlation factor g and the association constant K , for the carboxylic acids in various solvents are given in the Table 1. From the literature, it has been found that there is no general agreement regarding the dipole moment of the carboxylic acids. By using the molecular parameters¹⁸, bond angles and bond moment, the theoretical value of μ for a monomer acid is found to be 1.712 D.

It has been generally assumed by earlier workers^{10,11} that the acetic acid in the pure liquid state exists in a cyclic hydrogen bonded dimer. However, the existence of non-zero dipole moment value indicates that a portion of the dimeric units should be non-cyclic. And the experimental value of μ for carboxylic acid molecule found to be very much less than the theoretical value, shows the simultaneous existence of both ring dimers and open polymers¹². Many physicochemical studies^{13-14,17} reveal that the association is a mixture of non-polar dimer association and polar chain association. When the acids are diluted with the non-interacting solvents, such as CCl_4 and C_6H_6 , there is no possibility for the formation of hydrogen bonding between the solute and solvent molecules but the polymer may break and form open dimer. The non-zero dipole moment definitely indicates that even at infinite dilution the molecules are not cyclic dimer. The higher value of μ in C_6H_6 may be due to the π -electron interaction with the solute. The dioxane has a powerful anionoid centre capable of breaking down the molecular aggregates of the solute molecules and hence there is a predominance of monomer species. And these are bonded with the sp^3 bond of the dioxane leading to a higher value of μ than the theoretically calculated value.

From the above, it has been observed that the experimental value of μ follows the order, $\mu_{CCl_4} < \mu_{C_6H_6} < \mu_{dioxane}$.

The Kirkwood correlation factor g which is a measure of local ordering have both values, greater than unity and less than unity in the case of carboxylic acids (Fig. 1), and shows the parallel and antiparallel alignment with the neighbouring dipole. From the predominant configuration of an open dimer structure⁹, the calculated value of g is found to be 0.05 which is far below the experimental values. The higher values of g shows the presence of more number of monomers in addition to closed dimer, open dimer, trimer *etc.* In all cases, the value of g less than unity in CCl_4 and C_6H_6 shows that the dipole-dipole interaction of the aggregates of the solute makes the dipole almost anti-parallel with the field. But in dioxane, g is

TABLE 1—DIPOLE MOMENT, KIRKWOOD CORRELATION FACTOR AND DIMERISATION CONSTANT OF CARBOXYLIC ACIDS IN VARIOUS SOLVENTS

Substance	CCl_4			C_6H_6			Dioxane		
	μ Debye	g	K $dm^3 mol^{-1}$	μ Debye	g	K $dm^3 mol^{-1}$	μ Debye	g	K $dm^3 mol^{-1}$
Formic	0.84	0.96	2.37	1.69	1.01	9.58	2.10	1.09	4.87
Acetic	0.85	0.82	1.97	1.12	0.78	3.78	1.78	1.12	1.48
Benzole	0.89	0.52	0.68	1.02	0.46	2.76	1.92	1.15	11.82

Fig. 1. Variation of g with concentration of formic acid in various solvents.

found to be greater than one in all cases, which indicates the predominance of monomer species which are H-bonded with the solvent, and tends to keep the dipoles parallel to the field. Therefore, it is observed that the interaction between the dipoles are greater in dioxane than the non-interacting solvents CCl_4 and C_6H_6 . The association constants K for all cases are also given in Table I.

From the above, it is inferred that CCl_4 can be considered as the best solvent for studying the inter-molecular interactions. Though benzene and

dioxane have zero dipole moment, they cannot be used as a solvent.

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (P.T.) is thankful to U.G.C., New Delhi, for the award of Junior Research Fellowship.

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